

COMPATIBILITY ASSESSMENT BETWEEN INTERLEAVING POLYMER NANOFIBERS AND COMPOSITE LAMINATE RESIN

K. N. Shivakumar^{1*}, R. Panduranga¹, M. M. Sharpe¹, and S. G. Miller²

¹ Center for Composite Materials Research, Department of Mechanical Engineering
North Carolina A&T State University, Greensboro, NC 27411, USA

² NASA Glenn Research Center, 21000 Brookpark Road, Cleveland, OH 44135, USA

* Corresponding author (kunigal@ncat.edu)

Keywords: *Electrospinning, compatibility, interleaving, nanofibers, composite laminates*

1 Introduction

Fiber reinforced composite laminates are typically formed by laying up a multiple number of plies made of reinforcing fibers and resin, cured by applying heat and pressure or by using a catalyst-accelerator system. Due to multiple plies of different orientation, the interlaminar stresses build up at the laminate edges. Structural epoxies have poor interlaminar strength and toughness that causes premature delamination under load and ultimately leads to structural failure or loss of stiffness. Several methods have been reported over the years to enhance the interlaminar fracture toughness and delamination resistance of composite laminates, such as matrix toughening, optimization of stacking sequence, laminate stitching, braiding, edge capping, and critical ply termination. Alternatively ductile interleaving by polymer film in composite laminates was initially found to be attractive [1-3]. The film either blends with the parent resin during cure or deforms alone plastically to improve toughness. The approach quickly lost attraction because of increased weight/thickness and loss of inplane strength and stiffness. A similar concept that is becoming more attractive is the polymer nanofiber interleaving [4, 5]. Recent works in this area have been reviewed in [6, 7]. Shivakumar et al. [5] demonstrated that interleaving AS4/3501-6 composite laminate with nylon 6, 6 nanofibers produced by electrospinning increased the damping by 13%, reduced the impact damage size to one-third [8], increased fracture toughness and resistance by 150% and 30%, respectively, significantly increased delamination onset life; and increased the fatigue threshold energy release rate by 67% without any loss of in-plane stiffness and strength [9]. However, the more recent works of Ali et al. [10] with IM7-G/8552-1 and reactive polyethersulfone (r-PESU) nanofibers showed a 13% loss of compression strength. Thus

that not all combination of thermoplastic nanofiber and thermoset resin will lead to improved failure toughness. Hence there is need for assessing the compatibility of base composite resin with the polymer nanofiber. Furthermore, there is need to develop simple test methods to qualify the material combination. This paper focuses on identification and assessment of compatibility test methods for interleaved composite laminates.

2 Compatibility Test Methods

The conventional test methods [11] used for stiff and strong fibers such as fibers like glass, kevlar, and carbon with resin are not suitable for nano polymer fibers. Therefore qualitative test methods that provide a first approximate estimation of toughness improvement are chosen. They are: wettability, solubility, and peel tests. The details of each these test methods are discussed below.

2.1 Wettability Test

When a liquid resin drop is brought onto the solid surface, the contact of liquid/solid surfaces reaches an equilibrium condition based on the surface tension properties. Whether it will wet the surface or not depends on the relative magnitudes of the molecular forces that exist within the liquid and between the liquid and the solid. That can be measured by the contact angle between the liquid and solid (see Fig. 1). Smaller the contact angle better will be wettability. The contact angle θ is related to the surface properties of the nanofabric (f), the epoxy matrix (m), and air (a) systems by the Young equation as [12].

$$\cos\theta = \frac{\gamma_{fa} - \gamma_{fm}}{\gamma_{ma}} \quad (1)$$

where γ_{fa} , γ_{fm} , and γ_{ma} are the interfacial tensions between the fiber and air, the fiber and matrix, and the matrix and air, respectively. By conducting tests at different temperatures (room temperature to high temperature) the contact angle could be measured. This method is suitable to assess the compatibility of VARTM and RTM resins on nano fabric.

Fig.1. Schematic of the wettability test

2.2 Solubility Test

The second test is the solubility test, which addresses the survivability of the nanofibers during the cure cycle of the base resin. The test is different for liquid resin (VARTM/RTM) and autoclave prepreg resin. The two test methods are explained below.

2.2.1 Liquid Resin System

The principle of nanofiber solubility test for liquid epoxy resin involves submersion of nanofabric samples in the resin system; the temperature is varied as per the cure cycle and visually observing the sample till the resin gels. To conduct the test, mix the electrospun nanofabric (size about 10 x 10 mm²) in a clean glass beaker containing (room temperature) cure epoxy resin/hardener. Stir the mixture bottle with a magnetic stirrer for about 5 minutes. Visually observe the nanofabric for dissolving in the resin. If the nanofabric is not dissolved, continue the stirring till the resin system gels. This procedure can be repeated at elevated temperature. Insolubility of the nanofibers in resin is required to simulate the complex fracture process such as, nanofiber separation, pullout and fracture.

2.2.2 Prepreg System

This test is performed on a prepreg at elevated temperature to simulate cure cycle of matrix resin. The example describe here is for AS4/3501-6 prepreg. Similar procedure can be used for any prepreg. In this test method a nanofabric sample is

pressed over the prepreg ([0/90]) stack and then the whole assembly is heated over hot platens as per the cure of prepreg. By visually observing the solubility of the nanofibers in the resin matrix is assessed. The schematic of the test is shown in the figure 2. To conduct the test, 2 ply of 127 x 127 mm² square prepreg were cut; stacked in [0/90] sequence and then debulked. Carefully place the nanofabric specimen of size 102 x 102 mm² over the prepreg. Cover the assembly by nanofabric with release film and pressed by hand rollers. Sandwich the prepreg assembly between release film covered metal plates. The assembly is then placed over a hot plate maintained at stage I curing temperature of the prepreg (for e.g. 116 °C for AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy). Observe the nanofabric sample for every 15 minutes interval till the end of stage I curing and then set the temperature to final cure temperature of the prepreg (for e.g. 177 °C for AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy). Allow the prepreg assembly to cool to room temperature. Visually inspect the sample to check the solubility of the nanofibers in resin matrix.

Fig.2. Schematic of the solubility test

2.3 Peel Test

The peel test is similar to DCB test but is performed on a very thin laminate. The method directly measures the toughening of the interleaved nanofiber. In this test, the peel force is a measure of enhancement of toughness. The peel specimens can be made from any prepreg, the one for AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy is shown in figure 3. The ends of the specimens are pulled apart by controlling crosshead movement. The load and cross-head displacement, and crack extensions are recorded continuously. The schematic of the peel test is shown in figure 3. The average peel load per unit length is used to define the peel strength. Comparison of the peel strength of base and interleaved composite provides a

qualitative estimate of improvement of toughness by interleaving.

Fig.3. Peel test specimen. (a) Schematic (b) Photograph

3 Experimentation

3.1 Materials

The resin matrix system used for wettability test is given in Table 1. Aerospace grade AS4/3501-6 prepreg supplied by Hexcel Composites was selected for laminates. The polymers used to prepare electrospun nanofibers are Zytel 101 Nylon 6, 6 supplied by Dupont company and Virantage VW-10200 RP reactive polyether sulfone (r-PESU) and Radel R-5000 Polyphenylene sulfone (PPSU) were supplied by SOLVAY Plastics.

Table 1. Resin system used for compatibility assessment

Material	Supplier/Processing Condition
SC-15 Epoxy	Applied Poleramic Inc Resin/Hardener mix ratio: 100/30 Gel time: 3.3 h Cure: RT
SC-79 Epoxy	Applied Poleramic Inc Resin/Hardener mix ratio: 100/40 Gel time: 7 h Cure: RT
EPON 828 Epoxy	Miller-StephensonmChemical Company, Inc Resin/Hardener mix ratio: 100/40 Gel time: 138 mins, Cure: RT
URC-Epoxy	Uniter Resin Corporation Resin/Hardener mix ratio: 100/40 Gel time: 90 mins, Cure: RT
DERAKANE 510A-40 Vinyl Ester	Ashland Inc Resin/Catalyst/Accelerator mix ratio: 100/1.25/0.3 Gel time: 48 mins, Cure: RT

3.2 Electrospinning of Nylon 6,6, r-PESU, and PPSU

Electrospinning uses an electrostatic force to spin fibers from a polymeric solution. The details of the electrospinning principle can be found in ref. [4].

The dope solution was prepared by dissolving polymers in solvents. Electrospun nanofabrics were prepared by using an in-house electrospinning apparatus (figure 4a) composed of: (i) a high voltage power supply (ii) a syringe pump, (iii) two syringe assembly containing the polymeric solution, each syringe is equipped with stainless-steel blunt-ended needle and connected with the power supply electrode, and (iv) a grounded rotating collector. The precision syringe pumps feed the polymer solution to syringes that were positioned at the opposite sides of the collecting drum through Teflon tubes at constant volumetric flow rate. The electrospinning process parameters for different polymers are given in table 2. Fiber morphology was observed with a FEI XL30 scanning electron microscope (SEM) at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV. The SEM image of the electrospun Nylon 6,6 nanofabric is shown in figure 4b. The fiber diameter ranged from 67 to 198 nm. The measured average areal density of the nanofabric was about 2.47 g/m² with a standard deviation of 0.25.

Fig. 4. Electrospinning and morphology of electrospun Nylon 6,6 fibers (a) Setup (b) SEM micrograph.

Table 2. Electrospinning process parameters for different polymers

Electrospinning Parameters	Nylon, 6,6	r-PESU	PPSU
Solvent	Formic acid/Chloroform (75: 25 w/w)	Dimethyl acetamide	Dimethyl acetamide
Solution concentration, % w/w	12	27	27
Solution flow rate, ml/h	0.4	0.3	0.3
Spinning voltage, KV	35	40	40
Distance between needle and collector, cm	21.5	20.3	20.3
Drum linear speed, m/s	3	3	3
Spinning duration, h	7.5	8	8
Temperature, °C	22-26	22-26	22-26
Relative humidity, %RH	40-50	45-55	45-55

3.3 Fabrication of Laminates and Test Specimens

Two different tests required two different types of panels. Accordingly, base and interleaved thin laminates were fabricated for solubility and peel tests. Laminates of size 127 mm x 127 mm x 0.25 mm were fabricated for solubility specimens whereas panels of size 152 mm x 152 mm x 0.51 mm were fabricated for peel specimens. The peel specimens were made from prepregs (for e.g. AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy). A Teflon insert of 25 mm length was used as a delamination initiator between the top [0]₂ and bottom [0]₂ plies of prepreg. Spacer strips of 0.5 mm thickness were used to control the laminate thickness. The whole assembly was placed in a hot press and the prepreg was cured as per the specification of the prepreg supplier. The applied pressure is about 100 psi. The polymer nanofiber interleaved specimen is made by placing a layer of electrospun nanofabric at the mid-plane (delamination plane). The schematic of the laminate fabrication is shown in figure 5. Cut the panel to 152 mm (length) x 25 mm (width) size using tile saw. Due to the ultrathin nature of the laminates, integral flexible loading hinges can be made just by bending the specimens at a location 25 mm from the edge. To prepare the integral flexible hinges, bond the aluminum tape around the bent location and mark a line at a location 25 mm from the edges and then bend the specimens using straight edge.

Fig. 5. Schematic of laminate fabrication for peel test

3.4 Testing

Three types of tests were conducted, namely, wettability, solubility, and peel test. There were no standards for these tests in-house developed procedure was used. Measurements of the contact angle between the RT cure resin and the Nylon 6,6 nanofabric were performed by visual observation at room temperature. In order to obtain the contact angle of the polymer matrix on the nanofabric surface, drops were placed on the nanofabric surface and images were captured at different time intervals. In the experiments, a micro-pipette was used to control the volume of the drops. All tests were repeated three times for each type of the resin samples.

Solubility test is a visual observation test. Peel tests were conducted by opening the ends of the specimens by controlling crosshead movement, while the load and cross-head displacement are recorded continuously. The tests were conducted at displacement rates of 25.4 mm/min. The average peeling load per unit length was used to define the peel strength. Three specimens were tested for each sample.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Wettability

The wetting angle, θ between RT cure resins with the Nylon 6,6 nanofabric were measured by visual observation (qualitative). The experimental observations of different matrices are given in Table 3. The schematic of the resin drops at 0, 2, 5, 15, 45, and 90 minutes of time intervals are shown in the table. It can be observed from the table that at $t = 0$, the contact angle is less than 90° for SC-15, SC-79 and DERAKANE 510A-40 resin system which indicates that these resins wets the nanofabric. The

epoxy resin systems such as EPON828 and epoxy showed contact angles of approximately 90° at $t = 0$. This indicates that these resin's wettability to nylon 6, 6 is not good. It can also be observed from the table 3 that the spreading rate is different for different type of matrices. Both SC-15, SC-79 resins showed similar contact angles and spreading rate and showed almost complete absorption in the nanofabric after 90 min. Whereas resins such as EPON828 and URC-epoxy showed similar wetting characteristics with respect to contact angles and spreading rate. On the other hand, vinyl ester resin showed θ less than 90° at $t = 0$ and it spread quickly with time, thereby indicating wetting of the nanofabric. Vinyl ester resin showed no sign of spreading on the nanofabric and the shape of the resin droplets remained unchanged even after 90 minutes. Among all the resins, SC-15 and SC-79 showed lower contact angles and higher spreading rates. This can be attributed to the low viscosity (350 cps) and longer gel time (7 hours) of SC-15 and SC-79 epoxy resins in comparison to EPON 828 (1,210 cps, gel time 138 min) and epoxy (7,445 cps, gel time 90 min) resins. The figure 6 shows the photograph of the wetability test of various matrices on Nylon 6,6 nanofabric after 90 minutes. It can be observed from the figure that all the resin matrices wet the Nylon 6, 6 nanofabric. In the figure it can also be noted that SC-15, SC-79 epoxy resins spreads much better than EPON 828 and URC-epoxy resins and DERAKANE 510A-40 vinyl ester resin does not spread at all.

Fig. 6. Photograph of the wettability test after 90 minutes for various resin matrices

4.2 Solubility

The dissolution of nanofibers in 3501-6 epoxy resin is visually observed. Figures 7 and 8 shows the photograph of the laminates before and after the test. It is clear from the figure 8 that both r-PESU and PPSU nanofibers were completely dissolved in 3501-6 epoxy resin whereas the Nylon 6,6 nanofibers remain undissolved.

Table 3. Resin wettability visual observations

Time, minutes	Epoxy Resin				Vinyl ester
	SC-15	SC-79	EPON 828	URC-Epoxy	
0	Wetting, Contact angle less than 90° 	Wetting, Contact angle less than 90° 	Quasi wetting, Contact angle $\sim 90^\circ$ 	Quasi wetting, Contact angle $\sim 90^\circ$ 	Wetting, Contact angle less than 90°
2	Spreading in progress 	Spreading in progress 	Spreading in progress 	Spreading in progress 	No spreading
5	Spreading in progress 	Spreading in progress 	Spreading in progress 	Spreading in progress 	No spreading
15	Spreading in progress 	Absorption (little resin left on surface) 	Spreading in progress 	Spreading in progress 	No spreading
45	Spreading in progress 	Absorption (little resin left on surface) 	Spreading in progress 	No more spreading 	No spreading
90	Absorption (little resin left on surface) 	Absorption (little resin left on surface) 	Spreading in progress 	No more spreading 	No spreading

Fig. 7. Photograph of the solubility test laminates before curing. (a) Base (b) Nylon 6,6 nanofabric (c) r-PESU nanofabric and (d) PPSU nanofabric

Fig. 8. Photograph of the solubility test laminates after curing. (a) Base (b) Nylon 6,6 nanofabric (c) r-PESU nanofabric and (d) PPSU nanofabric.

4.3 Peel

The peel load-displacement response of base and nanofibers interleaved AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy laminates are shown in figure 9 through 12. From figures it is clear that both base and nanofibers interleaved AS4/3501-6 laminate showed initial linear response. For comparison purpose, the average load-displacement response of base and nanofibers interleaved AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy composite specimens is plotted in figure 13. From this diagram it is highlighted that the Nylon 6,6 interleaved laminate shows sudden drop in load after peak value whereas the r-PESU and PPSU interleaved samples showed gradual decrease of load after peak value. Table 4 summarizes peak load values for base and nanofibers interleaved AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy composite specimens. The average peak load of base AS4/3501-6 samples was about 5.7 N. The Nylon 6,6 interleaved sample showed an improvement of about 32% in peak peel load. Such an improvement can be attributed to the non-dissolvability of Nylon 6,6 nanofibers in 3501-6 epoxy resin. From the solubility tests it is clear that Nylon 6,6 fibers did not dissolve in 3501-6 epoxy resin and survived after cure. The survivability of nanofibers can lead to fracture morphology where events such as pull out, stretching, separation, and breakage of Nylon-66 nanofibers can occur and enhance fracture toughness. Whereas the r-PESU

and PPSU nanofibers interleaved sample showed about 9% increase in peak peel load. Such marginal peak load increase may be due to the dissolution of these nanofibers parent 3501-6 resin system and forming a tougher blend. However, fracture toughness and resistance enhancement may not be assured.

Fig. 9. Peel load-displacement response of base AS4/3501-6 laminate

Fig. 10. Peel load-displacement response of Nylon 6,6 nanofibers interleaved AS4/3501-6 laminate

Fig. 11. Peel load-displacement response of r-PESU nanofibers interleaved AS4/3501-6 laminate

Fig. 12. Peel load-displacement response of PPSU nanofibers interleaved AS4/3501-6 laminate

Fig. 13. Comparison of peel load-displacement response of base and nanofibers interleaved AS4/3501-6 laminate

Table 4. Peak peel load data for base and nanofibers interleaved samples

	B	C	D
15	Laminate		Peak Load, N
16			
17	Baseline		5.7 (0.69)*
18	Interleaved	Nylon 6,6	7.5 (0.78)
19		r-PESU	6.2 (0.0)
20		PPSU 5000	6.2 (0.56)

*standard deviation

4.4 Assessment

The solubility and peel tests were applied to: (i) base and Nylon 6,6 nanofibers interleaved AS4/3501-6 composites and (ii) base and r-PESU nanofibers interleaved IM7-G/8552-1 composites. From the solubility test it is very clear that Nylon 6,6 is not soluble in 3501-6 resin whereas r-PESU is completely soluble in 3501-6 resin system. Also, peel test results showed that the Nylon 6,6 interleaved AS4/3501-6 composite samples showed about 32% increase in peak peel load whereas the r-PESU and PPSU interleaved composites showed marginal increase in peak peel load. In order to relate the solubility and peel test results to the actual fracture test results it is worth reporting the fracture toughness of base and interleaved AS4/3501-6 laminates. Mode I fracture test results reported in ref. [4] showed that the Nylon 6,6 nanofibers interleaved AS4/3501-6 composite laminates increased the fracture toughness and resistance by 150% and 30%, respectively. Whereas the test results reported in ref. [8] showed that the fracture toughness of r-PESU nanofibers interleaved IM7-G/8552-1 composite laminates remained almost the same as the base laminate, whereas the fracture resistance (G_{IR}) increased with weight % of r-PESU, marginally at low nanofiber content and about 40% at 1.1%. From the comparison of test results of solubility, peel and fracture, it can be inferred that the non-soluble Nylon 6,6 nanofibers interleave which showed maximum peel resistance is a better candidate for fracture toughness enhancement. On the other hand, the soluble r-PESU nanofibers interleave which showed marginal improvement in peel resistance did not alter the fracture toughness of base laminate. More comprehensive tests are needed to correlate the peel resistance to the fracture toughness values.

5 Concluding Remarks

Three simple screening test methods were proposed to assess the compatibility between electrospun nanofibers and the resin matrix of the composite laminate. The tests are wettability (suitable for liquid resin used in VARTM/RTM), solubility, and peel tests. If they are satisfied then fracture toughness and resistance in the interleaved composite is expected to be higher. These tests were conducted on RTM, VARTM and prepreg resins. Wettability test is a quality control test, indicating the go and no-go results. If the resin is not wettable to nanofibers then the nanofabric is not be suitable for interleaving. Wettability tests showed that all the RT cure resin systems such as SC-15, SC-79, EPON 828, URC-epoxy, and DERAKANE 510-40A wet the Nylon 6,6 nanofabri;, SC-15 and SC-79 epoxies spreads better than EPON 828 and URC-epoxy resins. The DERAKANE 510A-40 vinyl ester resin does not spread at all thus indicating that Nylon 6, 6 interleaving is unlikely to improve the toughness. Solubility tests showed that r-PESU and PPSU nanofibers completely dissolved in 3501-6 epoxy resin whereas the Nylon 6, 6 fibers did not. Nylon 6,6 interleaved AS4/3501-6 samples showed about 32% increase in peak peel load whereas the r-PESU and PPSU nanofibers interleaved sample showed marginal increase (~ 9%) in peak peel load. Corresponding fracture toughness properties improved for Nylon 6, 6 and barely improved for r-PESU and PPSU. The present work demonstrated that simple test methods such as wettability, solubility and peel can be utilized to assess the nanofiber-matrix compatibility.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the support of NASA - Center for Aviation Safety (grant # NNX09AVO8A). Dr. Panduranga acknowledges the support of ARIS Inc. for the initial effort of this research.

References

- [1] W. S. Chan, C. Rogers, S. Aker "Improvement of Edge Delamination Strength of Composite Laminates using Adhesive Layers". *Composite Materials Testing and Design, ASTM STP 893*, pp 266-285, 1986.
- [2] J. E. Masters "Improved Impact and Delamination Resistance Through Interleafing". *Key Engineering Materials*, Vol. 37, pp 317-48, 1989.
- [3] F. Ozdil and L. Carlsson "Mode 1 interlaminar fracture of interleaved Graphite/Epoxy", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 26, No. 3, 1992.
- [4] Y. A. Dzenis and D. H. Reneker, "Delamination resistant composites prepared by small diameter fiber reinforcement at ply interfaces". Patent 6,2653,33. July 2001.
- [5] K. Shivakumar, S. Lingaiah, H. Chen, P. Akangah, G. Swaminathan and L. Russell Jr "Polymer Nanofabric Interleaved Composite Laminates". *AIAA Journal* Vol. 47, No. 7, pp 1723-9, 2009.
- [6] A. Zucchelli, M. L. Focarete, C. Gualandi and S. Ramakrishna "Electrospun Nanofibers for Enhancing Structural Performance of Composite Materials". *Polymers for Advanced Technologies*, Vol. 22, No. 3, pp 339-49, 2011.
- [7] K. Shivakumar and R. Panduranga "Interleaved Polymer matrix composites-A review", *AIAA-2013-1903*.
- [8] P. Akangah, S. Lingaiah, K. Shivakumar "Effect of Nylon-66 Nano-fiber Interleaving on Impact Damage Resistance of Epoxy/Carbon Fiber Composite Laminates". *Composite Structures*, Vol. 92, No. 6, pp 1432-39, 2010.
- [9] K. Shivakumar, H. Chen, M. Ali "Nanofabric Interleaved Composites for Aerospace Applications". *Journal of Aerospace Sciences and Technologies*, Vol. 64, No.1, pp 55-62, 2012.
- [10] M. Ali, R. Panduranga, M. Sharpe, S. Lingaiah, K. Shivakumar and S. Miller "Reactive Polyether Sulfone (r-PESU) Nanofiber Interleaved Composite Laminate", *Proceedings of SAMPE Tech 2012 Conference*, October 22-25, 2012, Charleston, South Carolina, USA.
- [11] D. Adams "Fiber-matrix interfacial bond test methods", *High-Performance Composites* 1 Jan. 2011 <<http://www.compositesworld.com/articles/fiber-matrix-interfacial-bond-test-methods>>.
- [12] K. Chawla, *Composite Materials, Science and Engineering*. New York: Springer-Verlag, pp 80, 1987.